

CHLORINATION OF METAL SULPHIDES. PART VI. CADMIUM SULPHIDE

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Chlorination of cadmium sulphide at elevated temperatures follows the same course as found earlier for zinc sulphide.

Optimum temperature for the reaction: $\text{CdS} + \text{Cl}_2 = \text{CdCl}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{S}_2$ has been found to be 500°. At this temperature, with a rate of gas flow of 6.35 c.c./min., chlorination can be carried out satisfactorily up to three hours by which time nearly 70% of the ore reacts and 60% of elementary sulphur is obtained. Beyond this transition point, sulphur has a tendency of being chlorinated.

By use of 10% by weight of carbon, the transition point can be shifted to about 90% progress of reaction (3 hours 45 mins.), affording nearly 80% yield of pure elementary sulphur. Use of sodium chloride as an incorporate does not offer any advantage in the reaction.

Results of chlorination of mixtures of zinc sulphide and cadmium sulphide are also shown.

In continuation of our work on the chlorination of metal sulphides¹⁻⁴ this paper presents the results of investigation on cadmium sulphide.

Although the only cadmium bearing mineral is the sulphide, greenockite, it never occurs as a separate mineral in sufficient quantities to be workable. It is usually mixed up with zinc blende, the proportion of cadmium sulphide being very low. It is thus not possible that chlorination of cadmium sulphide mineral would form a commercial process by itself for the recovery of elementary sulphur. But the investigation was considered useful in throwing light on the possible chlorination of zinc sulphide containing cadmium sulphide. Further, it would help in making generalisation on the behaviour of metal sulphides towards chlorination.

No information is available on the action of chlorine on cadmium sulphide; only Moyer⁵ reports the formation of cadmium chloride by heating the sulphide with hydrogen chloride.⁶

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement and procedure were generally the same as adopted earlier². Products of reaction were (i) cadmium chloride and unchanged ore remaining in the central zone of the reaction tube, within plugs, and (ii) pure elementary sulphur, sulphur contaminated with chlorine or a mixture of sulphur and its chlorides, depending on operating conditions. The latter products collected in the cooler parts of the exit end of the

reaction tube. At lower temperatures, however, some elementary sulphur sometimes remained in the central zone within the plugs.

When pure elementary sulphur was the product, it was carefully scrapped out and directly weighed to obtain the percentage yield. When it was contaminated with chlorine, it was boiled for a few minutes with water, carefully dried and then weighed. When proportions of chlorides of sulphur were relatively high, no attempt was made for determination of the yield.

For the determination of the progress of reaction, the product was leached with water to extract the cadmium. Determination of cadmium was carried out in the usual way using 8-hydroxyquinoline by the potassium bromate volumetric method. Conversion of cadmium sulphide into the chloride was taken as the progress of reaction.

For experiments with mixtures of zinc and cadmium sulphides, determination of both cadmium and zinc was carried out in the water extract of the product by polarographic method.

DISCUSSION

The first set of exploratory experiments was concerned with the chlorination at relatively high space velocity at different temperatures.

TABLE I

Preliminary experiments on chlorination of cadmium at different temperatures and for different extents of time.

Temp.	Duration of chlorination.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. sulphur.	Remarks.
300°	1 hr.	71.3 %	24.8 %	34.1 %	Chlorinated S
	3	90.4	6.1	37.0	Transition point passed at 2 hours.
400°	1 hr.	68.0	28.7	45.0	Tr. point not reached, but S is chlorinated.
	2 hr. 5 min.	92.8	4.7	50.1	Tr. pt. just reached.
500°	1	67.5	29.0	51.6	Tr. pt. not reached.
	1 57	79.0	18.3	54.5	Passed.

It would be obvious from data in Table I that the rate of chlorine flow was rather too high. The transition point was not sharp. In other words, some of the sulphur formed was slightly chlorinated even before the transition point was reached. A comparison of the columns 3 and 5 would show that the difference in the progress of reaction,

and the elementary sulphur formed decreased with increase of temperature. Thus, a higher temperature was in itself considered more favourable for

satisfactory formation of elementary sulphur. The proportion of sulphur dioxide formed was also higher. The particular sample of sulphide was found to contain about 2-3% of cadmium oxide. Thus, a high proportion of sulphur dioxide formation was ascribed to a reaction of type :

A purer sample was employed for the final experiments, and the experimental conditions adjusted on the light of the observations made above.

Reactions at different temperatures.—Reactions with lower space velocities of chlorine have been carried out at different temperatures and the results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Chlorination of cadmium sulphide alone at different temperatures.

CdS taken = 10 g. Duration of chlorination = 3 hours.

Rate of flow of chlorine = 6.35 c.c./min.

Temp.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. sulphur.	Transition point.
200°	62.0 %	34.0 %	42.1 %	2 hr. 15 min.
300°	63.0	30.0	50.0	2 hr. 45 "
400°	64.0	33.0	55.2	2 hr. 0 "
500°	70.0	28.0	60.0	Just reaching.
600°	59.0	37.5	49.5	2 hr. 5 min.

The general behaviour of the reaction was more or less the same as with zinc sulphide, e.g. at lower temperature there was really no sharp transition. With increase of temperature, the transition point became more defined. The difference in the extent of reaction (in three hours) at different temperatures was unusually low. This is due to the fact that the cadmium chloride formed tends to sinter or fuse (m.p. 568°). Actually the cadmium sulphide was found in the form of discs (inside the plugs in the central zone of the reaction tube) within which some cadmium sulphide was entrapped. The tendency of sintering would be pronounced with increase of temperature, and at 600° actual fusion took place. Thus, at this temperature, the extent of reaction was even less than that at 500°. In consideration of this, a temperature of 500° was considered optimum for the reaction under study. At this temperature the transition point was reached at nearly 3 hours after the reaction had proceeded to 70%. The sulphur formed was virtually pure.

Effect of different incorporations.—In view of the earlier work on zinc sulphide and cuprous sulphide, it was considered proper to attempt improving the conditions of reaction (shifting transition point towards the right) by use of incorporations at the optimum temperature of 500°. For comparison of results,

several experiments were carried out without any incorporate to study the progress of reaction with time. These results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

Progress of chlorination of CdS with time.

CdS used = 10 g. · Temperature = 500°. Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Time.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. S formed.	Remarks.
1 hr.	29.5 %	...	24.0 %	
2	51.5	46.0 %	42.0	Transition point was passed at about
3	70.0	28.0	60.0	
4	88.0	8.4	47.0	3hr. 5min.

Formation of CdCl₂ appears to proceed steadily, as also of the elementary sulphur. After the passing of transition point, however, the sulphur is very quickly chlorinated. Similar results with carbon incorporate are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Progress of chlorination of CdS in presence of carbon.

CdS taken = 10 g. Ultra carbon = 1 g. Temp. = 500°.

Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Time.	Progress of reaction.	Residual sulphide.	Elem. S formed.	Remarks.
1 hr.	21.8 %	...	13.5 %	Tr. pt. not reached
2	60.2	36.5 %	51.5	Do
3	77.5	19.0	67.0	Do
3 hr. 45 min.	90.0	6.8	79.5	Tr. pt. reached here.
4	93.5	3.5	59.5	

From the results a lower extent of reaction in presence of carbon is obvious. In the initial stages, some of the chlorine goes to be "bound" with the carbon. The shifting of the transition point by carbon incorporate must be primarily due to some chlorine being strongly bound by carbon according to the mechanism postulated by Emmet⁴ (see also references 2 & 3). In this particular case, as a secondary effect, it might improve the reaction by counteracting the fusion or sintering of the product. Improvement has been remarkable in that, by use of carbon it is possible to shift the transition point from 3 hours 5 mins. to 3 hours 45 mins. The reaction by that time proceeds to 90.0% and the yield of elementary sulphur (uncontaminated) comes to be as high as 80.0%. Beyond the transition point also formation of cadmium chloride continues fairly steadily on. That the sulphur is promptly chlorinated after the transition point would be evident. The difference between the progress of reaction and the yield of elementary

sulphur has been nearly 10%—a little higher than usually observed in earlier cases and ascribed to the sulphur dioxide being formed in the initial stages from moisture and air inside the reaction tube. The higher value with cadmium sulphide has been found to be due to the presence of about 1.5% of CdO in the sulphide.

Effect of using sodium chloride as an incorporate.—In the case of zinc sulphide, sodium chloride incorporate was found to retard the extent of chlorination and explained by suggesting the functions of a eutectic. In the case of cuprous sulphide, the rate of formation of copper chlorides was to some extent accelerated, as also the transition point. Results with cadmium sulphide are shown in Table V.

TABLE V
Chlorination of CdS in presence of NaCl.

CdS taken = 10 g. Temp. = 500°. Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

NaCl added.	Duration of expt.	Progress of reaction.	Residual sulphide.	Elem. S. formed.	Remarks.
Nil	2 hr.	51.5%	46.0%	42.0%	
5 g.	2	53.0	42.0	44.1	Transition
2	2	52.0	42.5	41.2	point at 2hr.
2	3	65.4	30.0	32.0	20mins.

In the case of cadmium sulphide, there seems to have slight, if any, effect on the rate of formation of cadmium chloride. The transition point is reached earlier—at 2 hr. 20 min., as against 3 hr. 10 min. without any incorporate. On the whole, the use of sodium chloride does not offer any improvement in this system. Incidentally, it must be pointed out that cadmium chloride also forms a eutectic with sodium chloride.

Chlorination of mixtures of cadmium and zinc sulphides.—Results of a few experiments of chlorination of mixtures of cadmium and zinc sulphides are presented in Table VI.

TABLE VI
Chlorination of mixtures of CdS and ZnS without incorporate.
Temperature = 500°. Duration of chlorination = 3 hrs.
Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

CdS taken.	ZnS taken.	ZnS reacted		CdS reacted	
		(as Zn).	%input.	(as Cd).	%input.
10 g.	Nil			5.4 g.	70.0
5	5 g.	1.1 g.	32.8	2.7	70.0
1	9	2.1	34.8	0.55	70.0
0.2	9.8	2.2	34.0	0.12	78.0

As would be expected from the relative affinity of zinc and cadmium for chlorine, there is not much preferential tendency of chlorination, but on the whole it can be said that cadmium sulphide has a greater tendency of chlorination. With a composition containing 2.0% or less of the cadmium sulphide, it seems possible that it can be fairly well separated as chloride, while the major portion of the ZnS remains unreacted.

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